

TEACHING TYPES OF LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS IN MOTHER LANGUAGE CLASSES (ON THE EXAMPLE OF ADJECTIVE AND NUMERICAL WORD GROUPS)

Abduvaitov Eldorbek Farxod ougli

Student of Chirchik state pedagogical university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8086568>

Abstract. *In this article, general information about linguistic analysis, types of linguistic analysis, the importance of teaching types of linguistic analysis in the mother tongue classes of general secondary schools, about the knowledge, skills and competences formed by students in linguistic analysis feedback and insights are provided.*

Keywords: *linguistics, analysis, complete and incomplete analysis, oral and written analysis, scientific principle, syntactic task, knowledge, skills, competence.*

INTRODUCTION

The analysis method is considered to be a very effective method in mother language teaching. By analyzing the exercises in the textbook, the teacher can explain to the student very well. We can observe several types of analysis. For example, phonetic analysis, lexical analysis, morphological analysis, syntactic analysis. Linguistic analysis is the study of a specific language or speech unit (word or sentence) based on the theoretical knowledge obtained, according to the requirements of each language science. Linguistic analysis creates the student's ability to use knowledge in practice. Through linguistic analysis, students gain a conscious, practical understanding of the essence of the given theoretical knowledge - linguistic rules. In the process of linguistic analysis, the student makes an independent observation on the knowledge and rules obtained in theoretical lessons, depending on a specific phenomenon of the language, and redevelops them in his mind. This ensures that the thoughts revealing the content of these events remain in the student's memory for a relatively long time. Only through analysis can one better understand the nature of some complex language phenomena.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Linguistic analysis with the student can be practically divided into two types:

1. Oral linguistic analysis.
2. Written linguistic analysis.

Oral linguistic analysis requires little time, allows to determine the student's knowledge of linguistics in a short period of time. In addition, the analyzing student will have the opportunity to help in time if he makes mistakes. This method of analysis is used more in the course of the lesson.

Written linguistic analysis also has its own positive aspects. A student analyzing a written text will have the opportunity to think freely. It can even use theoretical materials. Written linguistic analysis is mostly given as homework.

Types of linguistic analysis:

1. *Phonetic analysis*
2. *Spelling analysis*
3. *Orthoepic analysis*
4. *Lexicological analysis*

5. *Phraseological analysis*
6. *Semasiological analysis*
7. *Morphemic analysis*
8. *Morphological analysis*
9. *Syntactic analysis*
10. *Punctuation analysis*
11. *Methodological analysis*
12. *Etymological analysis*

Linguistic analysis is also divided into complete and incomplete analysis depending on the limit of coverage of language phenomena. A complete linguistic analysis of a text is a complex and time-consuming task. The examination of a text by all branches of linguistics is, literally, a complete linguistic analysis. Such an analysis cannot be used in the course of the lesson. In general, there is no need for such an analysis. A complete linguistic analysis would be appropriate if used in circles that study the language in depth. A complete analysis of a branch of linguistics is carried out in the last part of the hours given for that subject or when studying other further branches of linguistics. For example, a complete phonetic analysis is best done after all phonetics topics have been covered or between orthography lessons. The full analysis can also be used as a written work.

As a type of lesson, linguistic analysis should meet certain didactic and methodical requirements. Linguistic analysis must be fully compatible with the curriculum requirements for each branch of linguistics. Methodological and methodical requirements for the teaching of language sciences are also set before him.

The basic requirements for linguistic analysis are as follows:

1. Scientific principle.
2. The principle of working on the basis of a certain scheme.
3. The principle of not mixing one type of analysis with another type of analysis.
4. The principle of systolic skipping of the analysis.

RESULTS

It is known that grammar is a branch of linguistics that studies the grammatical construction of a language. Grammar is a set of rules about how words change and join together to form phrases and sentences. Grammar consists of two parts: morphology and syntax. Accordingly, grammatical analysis is divided into morphological analysis and syntactic analysis.

In the morphological analysis, word groups, their semantic types, grammatical categories, structural types and their function in the sentence are determined. Morphological analysis is directly related to syntactic analysis. For example, he did not meet the girl he adopted again. Let's analyze the given sentence. In this case, it becomes somewhat complicated to include another word in which category. Without further ado, let's move on to the syntactic analysis, and it will become obvious that the other word belongs to the ravish family. Because this word appears in the present tense. So, we will also learn the importance of parts of speech. Now let's pay attention to the sentence "Our neighbor's son is a good boy." In the analysis of this sentence, it is more difficult to determine the participle. The fact that he is a child cannot be taken as a determinative of what is good. It damages the meaning of the sentence. On the one hand, he is a good boy should be separated as a compound (complex) noun.

Adjective phrase analysis:

1. *Question*

2. *Level*
3. *Whether it is original or relative quality*
4. *Riding or not*
5. *Type of structure (simple, compound, compound, double, repeated)*
6. *The fact that the main current is artificial*
7. *Syntactic function in the sentence*

*Cabbage was covered with **white** snow, only the road was dark.*

White

1. *how?*
2. *additional level*
3. *original quality*
4. *did not ride*
5. *Simple*
6. *tub*
7. *determiner*

Analyzing the phrase number:

1. *Question*
2. *Type of meaning*
3. *Riding or not riding*
4. *Type of structure*
5. *Whether there are counting words or not*
6. *Syntactic function in the sentence*

*I bought **40 kg of silk** and **25 amirkons**, saying that I was in a hurry and caught the booty.*

40 kg of silk

1. *how much?*
2. *amount (number)*
3. *did not ride*
4. *Simple*
5. *kilo (measure of weight)*
6. *determiner*

25 amirkons

1. *how much?*
2. *quantity (number of pieces)*
3. *did not ride*
4. *joint*
5. *no*
6. *determiner*

CONSLUSIONS

In conclusion, each type of analysis needs to have strict goals and limits. This will strengthen the student's ability not to confuse one analysis with another. In this work, we focused on some of the linguistic analysis and showed examples. In the order of analysis, it is intended to show the main categories and characteristics of a certain field or series. The more we focus on the types of linguistic analysis in the mother tongue classes, the more we teach the students through different methods in each lesson, the more they knowledge, skills and competences in the field of

linguistics will increase. This will develop students' interest in science, the ability to independently interpret and analyze the meaning of each spoken word, and the ability to use it correctly in speech situations.

REFERENCES

1. Mahmudov N, Nurmanov A. va boshqa. Ona tili, 5-7-sinflar, 9-sinf. Toshkent: "Ma'naviyat", 2004. 76-b.
2. Mahmudov N, Nurmanov A. O'zbek tilining nazariy grammatikasi. Toshkent: "O'qituvchi", 1995. 235-b.
3. Gulomov A, Ne'matov Q. Ona tili ta'limi mazmuni, Toshkent: "O'qituvchi", 1998. 35- b.
4. Erkaboyeva N. O'zbek tilidan ma'ruzalar to'plami. Toshkent: "Yosh kuch", 2021.